

Reactions at the Surface of Hot Metallic Filaments.
Part III. The Reaction $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}$ on
Platinum coated with Barium Oxide.

BY B. S. SRIKANTAN.

The interaction of carbon dioxide and hydrogen at the surface of platinum is unimolecular. The order of the reaction being unity at the surface of a catalyst could be explained in a satisfactory manner by exactly the same assumptions as were made by Hinshelwood ("Kinetics of Chemical Change in Gaseous Systems," 1926, p. 148). If one of the reacting gases is adsorbed in preference to the other, the reaction rate is solely governed by the rate at which the molecules of the other gas strike those of the adsorbed one, provided every such collision is effective. In the reaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen at the surface of platinum and platinum-iridium alloys, described in the previous parts, it is difficult to judge if carbon dioxide or hydrogen, which is being preferentially adsorbed. But if the surface is coated with a thin layer of oxide it is possible that the oxide surface would be favourable for the adsorption of carbon dioxide to a greater extent than that of hydrogen and might lead to interesting results. With this object in view the reaction has been studied in detail at the surface of platinum wire coated with barium oxide.

The platinum wire (No.3), used for the experiments in Part I, was coated with a thin layer of barium oxide. The usual method of coating the wires with the help of paraffin sticks containing the oxide was not adopted, since it did not lead to satisfactory results. The coating peeled off and there was a tendency for the oxide to collect in small lumps at several places along the wire. So the wire was dipped in a concentrated solution of barium nitrate for a few minutes. Then it was slowly warmed up by sending a small current through it, just to drive off the water. This was repeated several times till a thin uniform layer of barium nitrate was formed on it.

Next the wire was electrically heated to bright redness in vacuum to decompose the nitrate and a little of the carbonate formed on it, and the apparatus was exhausted while heating the wire. Thus a uniform and thin layer of barium oxide was deposited on the surface.

The experimental methods were the same as in Part I. The temperature was calculated from the resistance of the wire on the assumption that the layer of oxide is a non-conductor.

At the temperature at which these reactions have been carried out, it should be remembered that most of the oxide would be converted into the carbonate and the surface would be composed of a mixture of barium oxide and barium carbonate. It is not impossible that the surface might be all of barium carbonate with a few specks of barium oxide, for the dissociation pressure of the former is 750 mm. at 1350°, 2.7 mm. at 1000° and 0.4 mm. at 915° (Frankelstein, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 1585; Johnston, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 1356). Hence the active catalyst in this instance is a few points on the surface, chiefly composed of the complex BaO, BaCO₃.

This catalyst was steady in activity and the results could be reproduced by working even at higher and lower temperatures alternately.

The Influence of Temperature.—The following tables give the data for the reaction velocity at different temperatures.

TABLE I.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 100.6 \text{ mm.}$		$P_{\text{H}_2} = 105.4 \text{ mm.}$	Temperature = 826°.
Time (secs.).	Pressure of hydrogen.	Instantaneous rates.	
0	105.4 mm.	—	
22	84.6	0.0100	
52	62.5	0.0100	
82	44.9	0.0109	
112	33.2	0.0099	
142	25.0	0.0093	
		Mean	0.0100

TABLE II.

$P_{CO_2} = 100.1$ mm.	$P_{H_2} = 102.1$ mm.	Temperature = 612°.
Time (secs.).	Pressure of hydrogen.	Instantaneous rates.
0	102.1 mm.	—
30*	99.9	—
270	88.9	0.000485
570	77.6	0.000452
870	66.9	0.000493
1170	57.9	0.000481
		Mean 0.000478

* The temperature was on the high side to start with and the time interval is short; so this reading is left out of consideration.

N. B.—The instantaneous rates are given by $dp/dt \times 1/P_{Hm}$ where dp is the change in pressure in time dt and P_{Hm} is the mean pressure of hydrogen in that interval.

TABLE III.

$P_{CO_2} = 101.8$ mm.	$P_{H_2} = 102.1$ mm.	Temperature = 769°.
Time (secs.).	Pressure of hydrogen.	Instantaneous rates.
0	102.1 mm.	—
30*	89.2	—
60	73.6	0.00689
90	60.1	0.00673
120	49.2	0.00665
150	40.2	0.00671
180	33.5	0.00606
		Mean 0.00651

* The temperature to start with was on the low side and hence this reading is left out of consideration.

Table IV gives the values of the temperature coefficients and the energy of activation E , calculated by Arrhenius's formula. The energy of activation and the temperature coefficient fall off with rise of temperature.

TABLE IV.

Temperature range.	Temp.-coeff. for 10°.	E .
612—769°	1.18	27,000 calories.
769—826°	1.08	15,000

The Influence of Pressure of Carbon Dioxide on the Reaction.— Experiments were carried out with 100 mm. of hydrogen and varying amounts of carbon dioxide in the system. The results are described in the following tables.

TABLE V.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 51.2 \text{ mm.}$		$P_{\text{H}_2} = 101.6 \text{ mm.}$	Temperature = 769°.
Time (secs.).	Pressure of hydrogen.		Instantaneous rates.
0	101.6 mm.		—
27	89.8		0.00457
57	77.8		0.00477
87	68.3		0.00433
			Mean 0.00456

Table III gives the data for 100 mm. of each of the gases.

TABLE VI.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 202.0 \text{ mm.}$ $P_{\text{H}_2} = 104.8 \text{ mm.}$ Temperature = 769°.

Time (secs.).	Pressure of hydrogen.	Instantaneous rates.
0	104.8 mm.	—
30	95.4	0.00313
60	86.0	0.00345
90	75.1	0.00451
120	64.2	0.00522
150	54.0	0.00575
180	45.0	0.00604
210	36.5	0.00695
240	30.0	0.00652
270	24.1	0.00727
330	16.0	0.00673
		0.00670 (mean of last five).

TABLE VII.

 $P_{\text{CO}_2} = 309.7 \text{ mm.}$ $P_{\text{H}_2} = 102.3 \text{ mm.}$ Temperature = 769° ,

Time (secs.).	Pressure of hydrogen.	Instantaneous rates.
0	102.3 mm.	—
30	81.1	0.00771
60	59.2	0.01040
90	40.8	0.0127
120	27.6	0.0125
160	18.8	0.0120
180	12.3	0.0139
		0.0129 (mean of last four).

TABLE VIII.

 $P_{\text{CO}_2} = 411.8 \text{ mm.}$ $P_{\text{H}_2} = 105.2 \text{ mm.}$ Temperature = 769° ,

Time (secs.).	Pressure of hydrogen	Instantaneous rates.
0	105.2 mm.	—
30	83.7	0.00768
60	61.4	0.0108
90	42.0	0.0125
120	28.8	0.0129
150	18.7	0.0135
		0.0127 (Mean of last three).

The results are represented in Fig. 1. It is rather peculiar that the reaction velocity is not constant from the beginning, but

Fig. 1.

slowly rises and then assumes a steady state. This initial rise is noticed in the experiments with 200, 300 and 400 mm. of carbon dioxide in the system. When there was only 100 mm. of carbon dioxide in the system, such a behaviour is not noticed. The results are rather difficult to explain on a quantitative basis. However, these results are enough to give us an idea of the relative adsorptive powers of the surface for these gases. The reaction velocity calculated with reference to carbon dioxide did not come out regular; but that calculated with reference to hydrogen gives fairly good constants except for the initial stages. In Fig. 2 these constants, obtained at the later stages, are plotted against varying quantities of carbon dioxide taken.

Fig. 2.

The increase of carbon dioxide in the system increases the reaction rate to a great extent till about 300 mm. of carbon dioxide, when it appears not to change with further increase. Carbon dioxide influences the reaction to a great extent, perhaps due to the tendency of BaO to add on to carbon dioxide and form BaCO₃.

Influence of Pressure of Hydrogen on the Reaction.—Experiments were performed with 100 mm. of carbon dioxide and varying amounts of hydrogen in the system. The results are described in the following tables. They show in a general way that hydrogen has a depressing effect on the reaction.

TABLE IX.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 103.0$ mm. $P_{\text{H}_2} = 56.5$ mm. Temperature = 760° .

Time (secs.)	Pressure of hydrogen.	Instantaneous rates.
0	56.5 mm.	—
30	49.8	0.00424
60	41.9	0.00574
90	32.1	0.00819
120	24.1	0.00949
150	18.0	0.00966
180	13.1	0.01040
210	9.9	0.00928
		<u>0.00940</u> (mean of last five).

Table III gives the data for 100 mm. of each of these gases.

TABLE X.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 104.3$ mm. $P_{\text{H}_2} = 209.5$ mm. Temperature = 769° .

Time (secs.)	Pressure of hydrogen.	Instantaneous rates.
0	209.5 mm.	—
30	206.9	0.000416
120	194.5	0.000686
180	184.5	0.000879
240	174.7	0.000926
300	164.3	0.001020
360	155.1	0.000960
420	146.7	0.000928
480	139.2	0.000880
540	132.7	0.000800
		<u>0.000888</u> (mean of last seven).

TABLE XI.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 100.0 \text{ mm.}$ $P_{\text{H}_2} = 307.1 \text{ mm.}$ Temperature = 769°.

Time (secs.)	Pressure of hydrogen.	Instantaneous rates.
0	307.1 mm.	—
60	287.1	0.00113
120	273.0	0.000815
180	260.5	0.000790
240	249.5	0.000720
300	237.4	0.000830
		0.000789 (mean of last three).

Here again the velocity coefficients do not come out constant from the beginning. There is an initial rise. The results are represented in Fig. 2. The velocity constants fall down to a low value with increase of hydrogen and then at about 200 mm. of hydrogen, the graph turns sharp and almost runs parallel to the X-axis, showing that further increase in hydrogen does not much affect the rate.

The above results were used to fit in equations of various types ordinarily found applicable for unimolecular and bimolecular reactions. The above method of representation was found to be best. However the results justify the conclusion that carbon dioxide is greatly adsorbed at the surface of the coated wire. The initial peculiarity could not be explained on a satisfactory basis. The activity of the wire was steady and the results could be reproduced.

Summary and Conclusions.

1. The interaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen has been studied at the surface of platinum wire coated with barium oxide. It is shown that the active catalyst in these experiments is a complex BaCO_3 , BaO . The reaction is unimolecular.

2. The temperature coefficient and the energy of activation fall off with rise of temperature.

3. Carbon dioxide is greatly adsorbed by the surface and the reaction rate increases with increase of carbon dioxide till 300 mm.

4. Excess of hydrogen has a depressing effect on the reaction.

5. With excess of either gas, constant velocity coefficients are obtained only after the reaction has proceeded some way, the initial peculiarity is too complicated to explain on any satisfactory basis.

I wish to place on record my thanks to Prof. H. E. Watson for his kind interest and helpful criticism.

DEPARTMENT OF GENERAL CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

Received September 27, 1929.

